

MODEL OF IMPROVEMENT OF MODERNIZED DIDACTIC PROVISION OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article examines the theoretical basis of improving the didactic support of the modernization of environmental education in the higher education system, the system and effectiveness of the improvement of the modernized didactic support of environmental education. Also, model of improvement of modernized didactic provision of environmental education in the higher education system were analyzed.

Key words: higher education, ecology, ecological education, ecological education, didactic, modernization, ecotheological, pedagogical, ecoethical, global, systematic analysis, pedagogical experiment, monitoring, adaptation, creative.

INTRODUCTION. Today, the organization of integrated education and the formation of various knowledge and skills of students on this basis remains one of the urgent tasks. Improvement of modernized didactic provision of ecological education is based on integrative education. Because the formation of ecological knowledge and skills based on the science of ethics and strengthening based on moral principles is carried out on the basis of integrated education. Before researching the problem of formation of ecoethical competence in students, it is appropriate to consider the essence of the competence and competent approach, conduct their analysis and analyze the social significance of the formation of competence in environmental ethics.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The issues of modernization of didactic support of environmental education are reflected in the scientific researches of classical period thinkers such as American and Western philosophers I. Kant, G. Hegel, I. G. Fichte, F. Schelling. Also I.L. Vershok, N.A. Sheyafetdinova, Y.A. Shishkina, YE.I. Balakina, E. Khoshimova, E. Karimova, Y. Shodimetov, S. Mamashokirov, E. Usmonov, H. Salomova, D. Rasilov, A. K. Berdimuratova, S. It was analyzed in the studies of Sanginov, Sh.P. Makhmudov, A. Akhmedov, A. Koldoshev.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Before researching the problem of formation of ecoethical competence in students, it is appropriate to consider the essence of the competence and competent approach, conduct their analysis and analyze the social significance of the formation of competence in environmental ethics. In our country, there are many masters of their profession - competent or skilled people - working in various fields. Many talented young people are studying in higher educational institutions, and there are also many young people who are taking up professions. All of them are gradually acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of studying, understanding why they are getting education. Summarizing all the experiences of the world up to this day, it can be said that education is a systematic, temporary, formal, relevant, means of imparting knowledge, skills, skills, and competence to prepare a person for life, including work.

Based on the above considerations, it is reasonable to call "competency-based education" rather than "competency formation" in the educational process. It can be defined as follows: Education based on the competence approach - by giving a person systematic, temporary, formal, relevant, knowledge, skills, qualifications, by giving him a certain skill, ability or competence level for life, including work (profession).) preparation tool. That is why "Education for sustainable development" can be called the preparation of a person at a certain level of competence within the framework of the systematic stages of education. In developed countries, people are hired not based on their college, bachelor's, master's, or doctor's degree or their code in the professional classification, but on the basis of their level of competence. For this purpose, computer tests, oral interviews and presentation evaluation criteria have been developed in a differentiated way depending on the position that the recruiter can occupy in the office, enterprise, organization or institution. The assessment criteria differ depending on the professional field of the employer, and the mechanism of its application has its own appearance. Summarizing the above considerations, it can be said that competence is the level of a person's ability to independently apply knowledge, skills, and abilities to achieve desired results.

In the theory of ecological education, the correct choice of the modern methodological basis, the placement of methods according to the types of education and the application of the methods based on its requirements, means the truthfulness, validity and practical significance of the obtained results.

Method (Greek *metodos* - way of knowing or research, theory, doctrine) - practical and theoretical acquisition of reality, mastering, learning, guidelines for knowledge, set of methods, separation of philosophical knowledge and justification method. A method is not a theory but a method used to conduct, substantiate, evaluate and conclude theoretical research. It is impossible to carry out any scientific and practical work without these research methods. We fully agree with the definition used in the international dictionary, that is, method (in Greek *metodos* - research way, method) is a way or method of achieving a certain goal. Although in the national literature, the method is referred to by different names - method, methodology, method, but it is appropriate to use the internationally recognized term "method" in scientific research. Methods exist in all disciplines, but in environmental education, it is necessary to select and systematize them based on their laws, goals and tasks.

Ecological research methods are a method of studying, identifying and implementing processes, phenomena, events, conditions and things in ecosystems. Ecological research is found in almost all branches of science, so it has the characteristic of complexity and is characteristic of almost all sciences, including pedagogical research methods are used. The main content of scientific methods consists of scientific theories tested in practice and essentially has the function of methods. The method, in turn, serves as a means of discovering new scientific theories and laws. The scientific method used to discover something new is more important, because other discoverers can make many discoveries based on the same scientific method used by the same scientist.

In the authoritative "Pedagogical encyclopedia" published in Uzbek language, two concepts were given to the term methodology: 1) it is a set of concepts and methods of doing something; 2) teaching about teaching methods. But: firstly, why in the pedagogical encyclopedia, as well as in the general national encyclopedia, the first option of the methodology, that is, the concept of universal recognition covering all aspects of personal

activity, is given; secondly, the methodology does not give the concept of doing work, implementation or fulfillment, but shows the process or technology of applying the methods of their execution; thirdly, a set of methods, or rather a methodology, performs the function of systematization; fourthly, as we mentioned above, teaching about teaching methods (methods) in pedagogy is educational methodology.

Pedagogical methodology is the principles, methods, methods, technique, procedure and organizational complex of conducting scientific research, that is, the research of pedagogical phenomena to solve the educational process. In our opinion, unlike pedagogical methodology, pedagogical methodology is not teaching about methods, but pedagogical methodology is planning, formalization, implementation, control, monitoring of pedagogical methods used in education and training based on certain pedagogical laws and regulations. a way, or rather a mechanism, of evaluation and conclusion.

A mechanism is a system of integrally connected parts necessary to perform any action. Pedagogical education methodology - from simple to complex, from close to far, taking into account the age, social and psychological condition of students, is divided into parts in accordance with the principles of education such as generality and universality.

The following requirements in the methodology of ecoethics education can be distinguished in the development of ecological ethical knowledge and skills in students: conducting research related to ecological education within the framework of certain ecosystems; when choosing methods, proceed from the current legal, social, economic, political, ecological, ethical and technological conditions; research of natural, socio-natural and natural-social events, processes and phenomena; selection of environmental education research methods; systematization of scientific methods based on real conditions. Therefore, in the methodology of ecological education, taking into account the social conditions, it is necessary to take into account the socialization of research, that is, the assimilation of the knowledge, norms and value system that allows a person to live in society.

Ecological moral education is one of the directions that allow to enrich and shape the spiritual and spiritual world of a person. Love for nature, plants, animals and people further develops in the hearts of students the feelings of goodness and kindness characteristic of a person. Careful preservation and respect of earth, water, air, plants and animals, sources of life and means of living is a criterion of spirituality. Knowing the laws of nature, applying them in practice, educating young people in the spirit of ecological culture ensures environmental cleanliness, health and well-being.

In the environmental education of students and young people at the stages of higher education, the main focus is on global skills related to ecosystems and environmental protection, rational and economical use of nature, and the use of technologies aimed at improving the environment. Also, attention is paid to issues related to sustainable development, knowledge of global and regional environmental problems. At the same time, the spiritual values of the Uzbek people, which are considered one of the main sources of ecological culture, are related to the protection, preservation, reproduction and transmission of values related to the preservation of nature, environment and cultural heritage to future generations. Qualities such as personal responsibility, conscientiousness, devotion to duty, determination, and initiative are formed and developed.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, the integrative methodology of improving the modernized didactic support of ecological education includes the educational model and technology based

on ecological moral knowledge, skills and competences. In this, special attention is paid not only to the formation of ecological knowledge, but also to the formation of an ecological and ethical worldview.

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